

MoveD – ORD Guidelines for Swiss Movement Laboratories

Terminology

Michelle C. Haas¹, Bettina B. Sommer¹, Simon van Rekum², Felix Moerman³, Eveline S. Graf¹

¹ ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences, School of Health Sciences

² ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences, University Library

³ ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences, President's Office

1. FAIR principles

FAIR principles are defined as follows and licenced under [CC BY 4.0 licence](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) by GO FAIR (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>).

Findable:

- (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- Data are described with rich metadata
- Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe
- (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable source

Accessible:

- Metadata and data are retrievable by their identifier (DOI; URI)
- Metadata are accessible even after data is no longer available

Interoperable:

- (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
- (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

Reusable:

- (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

2. Open data

“Knowledge is open if anyone is free to access, use, modify, and share it – subject, at most, to measures that preserve provenance and openness.” The full definition can be found at <http://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/>. This content is licenced under [CC BY 4.0 licence](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) by the Open Knowledge Foundation.

3. Metadata

According to (Jeusfeld, 2009) metadata specifies the following:

- How the data was created
- In which context the data can be used
- How data was transformed
- How data can be interpreted
- How data can be processed

4. Data processing vs. Data analysis

Data processing for the purpose of these guidelines is defined as all handling of data after the measurement session up to the point where revised data (through quality checks), e.g. angle data, is available. As soon as revised data is available, the analysis of the data begins. This rule applies to all different types of movement data.

5. Movement data

The following terminology is used in the guidelines below:

- “Gait analysis is a process of instrumented measurement and evaluation of walking ability ... and includes stereophotogrammetry, electromyography, and force plates” (Benedetti et al., 2017).
- Movement data includes all data that is collected in a movement laboratory and takes in stereophotogrammetry, electromyography, force plates for kinetics, accelerometry, inertial measurement units, electroencephalography, plantar pressure sensors, imaging (ultrasound, magnetic resonance imaging, computer tomography), and two-dimensional video data.

A terminology matrix for all EMG-related terms can be found in McManus et al., 2021.

Table 1: Definition of the components of movement data as used in these guidelines.

Term	Definition (as used in these guidelines)	Reference
Electromyography (EMG)	“An experimental technique concerned with the development, recording, and analysis of myoelectric signals. Myoelectric signals are formed by physiological variations in the state of muscle fibre membranes.”	Basmajian & De Luca, 1985
Stereophotogrammetry	Marker based or markerless motion capture through optoelectronic sensors	
Kinematics	Motion of objects without reference to the forces which cause the motion	Oxford English Dictionary, 2023
Kinetics	The science that describes the effects of forces acting on a body	
Spatiotemporal parameters	Parameters connected with the position (spatial) and the time (temporal) of motion	Oxford English Dictionary, 2023b
Accelerometer	Accelerometers measure applied acceleration acting along a sensitive axis which can be used to measure body movement in up to three planes	Godfrey et al., 2008
Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU)	“Inertial measurement units are wearable sensors that contain an accelerometer, a gyroscope and sometimes a magnetometer. They measure linear acceleration and angular velocity”	McGrath et al., 2021
Electroencephalography (EEG)	“Recording of the electrical activity of the brain by means of electrodes placed on the scalp”.	Oxford English Dictionary, 2023a
Plantar pressure	The measurement of pressure distribution on the plantar surface of the foot.	
Imaging	“The use of electromagnetic or ultrasonic radiation to produce images of organs and tissues within the body for diagnostic or screening purposes.” e.g. Ultrasound,	Oxford English Dictionary, 2024

	magnetic resonance imaging, and computer tomography	
Two-dimensional video	"The process of recording moving visual images in a digital format".	Oxford English Dictionary, 2024b

6. Anonymized vs. encoded data

6.1. Context

Bear in mind that **anonymized and encoded data are not the same!** Anonymized data refers to information that has been irreversibly altered or stripped of any identifying characteristics. It is thus no longer possible for anyone to trace back to an individual's identity. Encoded (or encrypted) data, on the other hand, is transformed through a systematic process into a different format but can be reversed to its original form by whoever has access to the key. Whether data are anonymized or encoded has legal implications: fully anonymized data are technically no longer considered personal data and are therefore in principle not subject to data protection law, whereas encoded data are. However, since it is difficult to clearly pinpoint sufficient anonymization, researchers should be encouraged to curate even anonymized data according to the security standards proposed in these guidelines. De-identification can be considered part of both anonymization or encoding and concerns the technique of removing direct identifiers or quasi identifiers.

Encoded data according to the Ordinance on Human Research with the Exception of Clinical Trials, 2014, Article 26:

"1. Biological material and health-related personal data are considered to be correctly coded in accordance with Article 32 paragraph 2 and Article 33 paragraph 2 HRA if, without access to the key or to the source data, it is only possible with disproportionate effort to link the biological material or the health-related data to a specific person.

2. Coding must be effected using a method based on the current state of the art. The key must be stored separately from the biological material or personal data and in accordance with the principles of Article 5 paragraph 1, by a person or organisational unit to be designated in the application, not involved in the research project."

Anonymisation according to the Ordinance of Human Research with the Exception of Clinical Trials, 2014, Article 25:

"1. For the anonymisation of biological material and health-related personal data, any association with a specific person must be rendered impossible or eliminated in such a way as to allow this association to be re-established only with disproportionate effort.

2. Anonymisation must be effected using a method based on the current state of the art. In particular, items of data which, individually or in combination, allow the association with a specific person to be re-established, such as the first name, surname, address, date of birth or unique identification numbers, must be deleted or modified.

3. The method used for anonymisation must be documented, including a description of the residual risk of reidentification."

Anonymisation and coding according to Federal Act on Research Involving Human Beings, 2014, Article 35:

"The Federal Council shall specify the requirements for correct and secure anonymisation and coding and also the conditions for breaking the code".

A guide to anonymization in accordance with the law, in German, can be found at <https://www.edoeb.admin.ch/edoeb/de/home/suche.html#leitfaden%20technische%20und%20organisatorische%20massnahmen%20zum%20datenschutz>. In this guide entitled “Technische und organisatorische Massnahmen zum Datenschutz”, anonymization is defined as the process during which personal data and any possibility of recovering the original data are permanently removed. The person can thus no longer be identified, and the process is irreversible.

6.2 Resource: Data de-identification of health-related data

The recommended phase approach includes suggestions for the definition of direct identifiers. A template for use case evaluation and risk assessments is also linked to the phase approach. This is similarly available from <https://sphn.ch/document/template-use-case-evaluation-and-risk-assessment/>

When using the template for use case evaluation and risk assessments, please consider the following points:

Tab “IT security and contractual measures”

- C-06-01: A variable is considered as one outcome e.g. the angle data of one joint, one leg, and in one direction
- C-10-03: A university is considered to be an external user from the public sector if a university is to have other access in addition to the main project site
- C-12-01-01: This is only applicable to movement laboratories located in a hospital.

Tab “Data de-identification”:

- D-04: If research is performed with living persons, this part can be ignored.
- D-06: If professions of participants have not been collected, this part can be ignored.
- D-07: If locations of participants have not been collected, this part can be ignored.
- M-03: This is usually only applicable to movement laboratories located in a hospital.
- DCM-01-DCM-06: Only relevant when DICOM attributes (medical imaging information) have been collected. Otherwise, this part can be ignored.
- G-01: Not relevant for movement labs and can therefore be ignored.

Recommended phase approach by Swiss Personalized Health Network available at <https://sphn.ch/document/data-de-identification-recommended-phased-approach/>

6.3 Comment of project team:

Research data from human movement laboratories often consist of individual movement patterns which can be considered as identifying information and can hence be personal data. Individual datasets of data from movement laboratories cannot therefore be fully anonymized. Means and standard deviations over multiple people are, however, anonymous as no reference can be made to the individual anymore. Since, from a legal point of view, a big difference exists between laws which are applicable to anonymous or encoded data, we will highlight what is relevant in each case. In this written form of the guidelines, sections that are important ONLY for encoded data and NOT FOR anonymous data are highlighted in **yellow** and labelled accordingly.

7. References

- Basmajian, J. V., & De Luca, C. J. (1985). *Muscles alive: Their functions revealed by electromyography* (5th ed). Williams & Wilkins.
- Benedetti, M. G., Beghi, E., De Tanti, A., Cappozzo, A., Basaglia, N., Cutti, A. G., Cereatti, A., Stagni, R., Verdini, F., Manca, M., Fantozzi, S., Mazzà, C., Camomilla, V., Campanini, I., Castagna, A., Cavazzuti, L., Del Maestro, M., Croce, U. D., Gasperi, M., ... Ferrarin, M. (2017). SIAMOC position paper on gait analysis in clinical practice: General requirements, methods and appropriateness. Results of an Italian consensus conference. *Gait & Posture*, *58*, 252–260.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2017.08.003>
- Federal Act on Research Involving Human Beings, Pub. L. No. AS 2013 3215, 810.30 35 (2014). <https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/cc/2013/617/en>
- Godfrey, A., Conway, R., Meagher, D., & ÓLaighin, G. (2008). Direct measurement of human movement by accelerometry. *Medical Engineering & Physics*, *30*(10), 1364–1386.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.medengphy.2008.09.005>
- Jeusfeld, M. A. (2009). Metadata. In L. LIU & M. T. ÖZSU (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Database Systems* (pp. 1723–1724). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-39940-9_893
- McGrath, J., Neville, J., Stewart, T., & Cronin, J. (2021). Upper body activity classification using an inertial measurement unit in court and field-based sports: A systematic review. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part P: Journal of Sports Engineering and Technology*, *235*(2), 83–95.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1754337120959754>
- McManus, L., Lowery, M., Merletti, R., Søgaard, K., Besomi, M., Clancy, E. A., Van Dieën, J. H., Hug, F., Wrigley, T., Besier, T., Carson, R. G., Disselhorst-Klug, C., Enoka, R. M., Falla, D., Farina, D., Gandevia, S., Holobar, A., Kiernan, M. C., McGill, K., ... Hodges, P. W. (2021). Consensus for experimental design in electromyography (CEDE)

project: Terminology matrix. *Journal of Electromyography and Kinesiology*, 59,
102565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelekin.2021.102565>

Ordinance on Human Research with the Exception of Clinical Trials, Pub. L. No. AS 2013
3381, 810.301 26 (2014). <https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/cc/2013/642/en>

Oxford English Dictionary. (2023a). *Electroencephalography*, *n.* Oxford University Press;
Oxford English Dictionary. <https://doi.org/10.1093/OED/1205469066>

Oxford English Dictionary. (2023b). *Kinematic*, *adj.*, *sense 1.a.* Oxford University Press;
Oxford English Dictionary. <https://doi.org/10.1093/OED/8968364951>

Oxford English Dictionary. (2023c). *Spatio-temporal*, *adj.* Oxford University Press; Oxford
English Dictionary. <https://doi.org/10.1093/OED/5931114084>

Oxford English Dictionary. (2024a). *Medical imaging*, *n.* Oxford University Press; Oxford
English Dictionary. <https://doi.org/10.1093/OED/7258489305>

Oxford English Dictionary. (2024b). *video*, *adj.* & *n.* Oxford University Press; Oxford English
Dictionary. <https://doi.org/10.1093/OED/7922527730>